

Research Article

Comparison of Different Techniques for the Isolation of *Rhizoctonia solani* from Infected Potato Tubers

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ABSTRACT

The effect of surface disinfection, temperatures, nutrients and chemicals on sclerotial germination of *Rhizoctonia solani* from potato tubers were studied on potato dextrose agar (PDA). Germination occurred from tuber pieces bearing sclerotia pre-treated for one min with 0.1% of mercuric chloride. Tuber pieces pretreated with 0.5% and 1% of mercuric chloride for various lengths of times, including 15 sec, 30 sec and one min showed no sclerotial germination on PDA. Similarly sclerotial germination did not occur after pretreated with sodium hypochlorite for same concentrations and times. Sclerotial germination was optimal at a temperature of 25° C on PDA. Germination of sclerotia was best on PDA followed by cornmeal agar (CMA). Minimum mycelial growth occurred on water agar (WA) while sclerotial germination was minimal on malt extract agar (MEA) after one week of inoculation. Tuber pieces bearing sclerotia were also treated with 0.1 % of mercuric chloride, sodium hypochlorite, potassium hydroxide and ethanol for one min before inoculation but no sclerotial germination occurred on PDA except from pieces treated with mercuric chloride.

Keywords:

Sclerotial Germination, Mycelial Growth, Inoculation, PDA.

INTRODUCTION

Potato (*Solanum tuberosum* L.) is one of the most important vegetable crops of the world. In Pakistan it excels in production and consumption among all vegetables. Fortunately the environment of Pakistan as well as that of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa is suitable for cultivation and production of crop. According to agricultural statistics potato occupied an area of 145000 ha in Pakistan during 2008 with a production of 2941300 tons while in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa it occupied an area of 9100 ha with a production of 121000 tons (agriculture statistics of Pakistan, 2008-09).

However in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa the production of potato is very low as compared to its potential. Susceptibility of the crop to diseases is one of the reasons of low production this crop. There are many diseases such as black scurf, stem canker, late and early blight which greatly reduce the quantity and quality of potatoes. Black scurf caused by *Rhizoctonia solani* is endemic and occurs in many potato producing areas of the world including Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (Banville 1978, 1989; Powel sonet *al.* 1993; Banville *et al.* 1996). Black scurf is an economically important disease, causing both qualitative and quantitative damage to potato crops worldwide (Tsrer, 2009). Quantitative losses occur due to infection of stems, stolons, and roots, which affect tuber size and number (carling *et al.*, 1989; Platt 1989). Qualitative losses occur mainly through the production of disfigured tubers and the development of sclerotia on the tuber surface (James and McKenzie, 1972). *Rhizoctonia* potato disease has been reported to cause marketable losses of up to 30% (Wienhold *et al.*, 1982; Banville, 1989; Platt *et al.*, 1993). *Rhizoctonia solani* is a very common soil borne pathogen with a great diversity of host plants (Agrios, 1988). It is the imperfect state of the basidiomycete fungus that does not produce sexual spores. In nature *Rhizoctonia* exist as vegetative mycelium and sclerotia consists of loosely constructed knots of melanised hyphae, with no cellular differentiation into a rind or medulla (Townsend and Willets, 1954; Webster, 1980). Sexual spores are produced occasionally and were first observed by Prillieux and Delacroix, (1891). The sexual stage of *Rhizoctonia solani* is known as *Thanatephorus cucumis* (Frank Donk). The characterization of *R. solani* was given by Ogoshi (1987) and Sneh, (1996). The pathogen has;

1. Pale to dark brown mycelium with larger hyphae diameter with branching near the distal septum of hyphal cell, often at nearly right angles to hyphae.
2. Formation of septum in the branch near the origin.
3. Constriction of the branch at the origin.
4. Production of sclerotia of various shapes and sizes.
5. Multinucleate cells.

6. No clamp connection.
7. Sclerotia not differentiated into rind and medulla.

Anastomosis groups (AGs) of *Rhizoctonia* are the isolates which have the ability to recognize and fuse with each other thus regarded is genetically related, where the isolate that does not have this ability are genetically unrelated (Parmeter *et al.*, 1969). If hyphal anastomosis occur between the paired isolates these are considered to belong with the same anastomosis groups (Ogoshi, 1987). It has been observed that Isolation of *Rhizoctonia solani* from sclerotia in vitro is difficult and cumbersome. Germination of sclerotia is affected by many factors including temperature, pH, culture medium, incubation temperature (Ritchie, 2009) and surface sterilization with disinfectants. These factors must be optimized to make isolation from potato tubers a success. The main objectives of the current research are to compare different techniques for the isolation of *Rhizoctonia solani* from potato tubers and to find out an easy way for isolation of *Rhizoctonia solani* from potato tubers.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Collection of potato tubers:

The infected potato tubers showing obvious scurf (sclerotia) were collected from a local market in Peshawar. Infected tubers containing sclerotia (Fig. 1) placed in paper bags. The sample bags were appropriately labeled and stored at 4°C in the department of Plant Pathology, KPK Agricultural University Peshawar for further use.

Surface disinfection of tubers

Small pieces of potato tubers bearing sclerotia were excised from the surface of tubers with a sterile scalpel. The pieces were then pre-treated with mercuric chloride at different concentration for various lengths of time. The disinfectant concentration were 0.1%, 0.5%, and 1%, and seed pieces were treated for 15sec, 30sec and 1 min with each concentration, respectively. The treated tuber pieces were afterward dipped in sterile distilled water to remove the excess of disinfectant and then allowed to dry on sterile filter papers. Sclerotia were then plated on potato dextrose agar (PDA) medium under aseptic condition; plates were sealed with parafilm to avoid contamination. The plates were then incubated at 25°C until colonies developed.

A second surface disinfectant test included sodium hypo chloride at different concentration for various lengths of time. Concentrations and treatment time was the same.

Isolation on different culture media

Sclerotia were carefully excised from potato tubers with the help of a sterile scalpel. The pieces were pretreated with 1% mercuric chloride for 1 min and then washed in sterile distilled water to remove the surface residues. Sclerotia were allowed to dry on sterile filter papers. The pieces were then plated on various media including potato dextrose agar (PDA), malt extract agar (MEA), corn meal agar (CMA), and water agar (WA) media in aseptic condition. Each treatment was repeated four times and arranged as CR design. The plates were sealed with parafilm to avoid contamination and then incubated at 25°C until sclerotia germinated.

Pre -heat treatment

Small pieces of potato tuber bearing sclerotia were --- from tuber surface with help of a sterile scalpel. Pieces were then dipped in a flask (225ml) containing distilled water . A thermometer was suspended in each flask to record the temperature. The flask was then kept in a water bath which was-set on the ---- temperatures. The flask was maintained on that specific temperature for five min. Temperatures used were 25°C, 30°C, 35°C and 40°C. The treated tuber pieces were then allowed to dry on sterile filter papers. The pieces were then plated on PDA culture medium under aseptic condition. Each treatment was replicated four times and the experiment was set as completely randomized design.

Effect of incubation temperatures

Small pieces of potato tubers bearing sclerotia excised from potato tubers were pretreated with 0.1% mercuric chloride for 1 min for surface disinfection. After a thorough wash in distilled water pieces were then allowed to dry on sterile filter papers and then plated on PDA in a laminar flow unit. The plates were then sealed with parafilm and incubated at various incubation temperatures including 25° C, 30° C, 35° C and 40° C. Each treatment was replicated four times and plates were arranged in a CR design.

Chemical treatment of sclerotia

Potato pieces bearing sclerotia were excised with the help of a sterile scalpel and treated with a range of different

chemicals includes ethanol, potassium hydroxide, mercuric chloride and sodium hypochlorite at a rate of 1% for 1 min in order to give them a chemical shock before germination. Following treatment with the above chemical agents the pieces were dipped in sterile distilled water to remove excess of the chemicals. The pieces were then plated on PDA under aseptic conditions. Each treatment was replicated four times. Plates were sealed with parafilm to avoid contamination and arranged in CR design at 25°C until sclerotial germination.

Statistical analysis

Data were subjected to analysis of variance under CR (completely randomized) design. Treatments showing significant variations were separated by least significant difference test.

RESULTS

Effects of Surface disinfection

The results given in Table 1 were significant at 5% level of probability. Good isolation of *Rhizoctonia solani* was observed from tuber pieces (bearing sclerotia) which were treated with 0.1% mercuric chloride for one min, on PDA. Colony diameter reached up to 7.15 cm following seven days of incubation. The pieces which were treated with other concentrations of mercuric chloride for various lengths of time did not show any fungal growth. Similarly tuber pieces pretreated with various concentrations of sodium chloride for different lengths of times also did not support any growth on PDA. .

Effect of culture media

Following inoculation, significant ($p < 0.05$) differences were found in colony diameter of *Rhizoctonia solani* (Table. 2).with respect to different media the highest colonies diameter(7.2 cm) was found on PDA followed by cornmeal agar (5.5cm).Colony diameter on water agar(WA) was 2.8cm while the least colony diameter 0.1cm appeared on malt extract agar culture medium.

Table-1: Mean colony diameter(cm) of *Rhizoctoniasolani* after seven days of incubation, from sclerotia, pretreated with various concentrations of mercuric chloride for different lengths of time.

Concentration/time	Colony diameter		
	15 sec	30sec	1 min
0.1%	0.00 B	0.00 B	7.175 B
0.5%	0.00 B	0.00 B	0.00 B
1%	0.00 B	0.00 B	0.00 B

LSD value=0.2828

Means followed by different letter(s) in the same column are significantly different from one another at 5% level of probability.

Table 2. Means colony diameters (cm) of *Rhizoctoniasolani* on different media at % level of probability.

Media	Colony diameter (cm)				
	R1	R2	R3	R4	Mean
PDA	7.7	6.0	7.3	8.0	7.250 A
CMA	5.8	4.9	6.0	5.5	5.550 B
WA	3.4	2.9	3.0	2.1	2.850 C
MEA	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.3	0.100 D

LSD value -0.8864

Means followed by different letters are significantly different at 5% level of probability from one another.

4.3 Effect of pre heated treatment

Statistically significant results were obtained at 5% level of probability when tuber pieces bearing sclerotia were heat treated at different temperatures for 5 min. The maximum colony diameter (7.688 cm) was observed from pieces heated at 25°C before plating followed by that of 30°C (6.500cm) Table 3. The colony diameter from potato pieces heated at 35°C was (0.7500 cm) and the lowest colony diameter (0.07500 cm) on PDA was observed from pieces pre heated at 40°C after seven days of incubation.

4.4 Effect of incubation temperatures

Table 4 shows that the colony diameter of *R.solani* from tuber pieces inoculated on PDA are significantly different at 5% level of probability with respect to incubation

temperatures. The highest colony diameter (7.5 cm) was observed at 25°C for seven days. The second highest colony diameter (5.8cm) was observed on plates incubated at 30°C. The lowest colony diameter (0.2cm) was recorded on plates which were kept at 35°C for seven days. Conversely no growth was observed on plates maintained at 40°C.

4.5 Effect of various chemicals on sclerotial germination

The highest colony diameter (6.5cm) was found in case of tuber pieces bearing sclerotia, treated with 0.1% of mercuric chloride for one min. The tuber pieces treated with the same concentration and time of sodium hypochlorite, ethanol and potassium hydroxide did not show any sclerotial growth on PDA culture medium.

Table 3. Mean colony diameter (cm) of *Rhizoctonia solani* after seven days of inoculation on PDA from sclerotia treated at different temperatures for 5 min.

Temperatures	Colony diameter (cm)				
	R1	R2	R3	R4	Mean
25°C	7.8	7.1	7.3	8.4	7.886 A
30°C	6.9	6.0	7.3	5.8	6.500 B
35°C	1.3	0.8	0.0	0.9	0.750 C
40°C	0.0	0.0	0.3	0.0	0.075 C

LSD value=0.8311

Means followed by different letters are significantly different at from one another at 5% of probability.

Table 4. Means colony diameter (cm) of *Rhizoctonia solani* after seven days of inoculation on PDA placed at different incubation temperatures.

Incubation temperatures	Colony diameter(cm)				
	R1	R2	R3	R4	Mean
25°C	7.1	7.3	8.0	7.5	7.885A
30°C	5.9	5.0	6.1	6.3	5.855B
35°C	0.1	0.0	0.3	0.4	0.20 C
40°C	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.00 C

LSD value =0.5455

Means followed by same letters are significantly not different at 5% percent level of probability.

Table 5. Means colony diameter (cm) of *Rhizoctonia solani* from tuber pieces treated with different chemicals.

Chemicals	Colony diameter(cm)				
	R1	R2	R3	R4	Mean
Mercuric chloride	7.8	7.5	6.9	6.5	6.5 A
Sodium hypo chloride	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.00 B
Potassium hydroxide	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.00 B
Ethanol	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.00 B

LSD value =0.3468

Means followed by same letters are not significantly different from one another.

Fig.1 Potato tubers bearing sclerotia of by black scurf fungus *R.solani*.

Fig.2 Colonies of *Rhizoctonia solani* on PDA.

Fig .3Hyphal growth of *Rhizoctonia solani*, isolated from infected potato tubers, on PDA.

DISCUSSION

Black scurf of potato, caused by *Rhizoctonia solani* is a worldwide occurring disease including Pakistan as well as Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. Sclerotia are the characteristic signs of disease. Isolation of the pathogen from sclerotia is tedious and needs standardization. The recorded data showed that germination of sclerotia differs with different techniques. Germination is greatly depends on temperature, nutrient and chemicals. The results of temperature treatment showed better mycelium growth at 25° C and 30° C than higher temperatures. The previous research also showed that the optimal temperatures for the growth of all isolate of *Rhizoctonia solani* is between

22 and 25° C (Chand and Logan, 1993). Sclerotial germination on potato dextrose agar (PDA) and cornmeal agar (CMA) were better than water agar (WA). The growth of *Rhizoctonia solani* is higher on nutrient rich media as compared with nutrient poor media (DIJST, 1988). Malt extract (MEA) agar showed poor sclerotial germination. Malt extract agar contains nutrients in the form of complexes so the fungus may take time to convert these complexes into degradable form. Pretreatment for one minute with 0.1% mercuric chloride allowed sclerotial germination while higher concentrations e.g. 0.5% and 1% did not allow any fungal growth. Observing this result it may possible that higher

concentrations of mercuric chloride affect the actual ingredients of sclerotia and check its growth.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

- *Rhizoctonia solani* can be easily isolated from potato tuber pieces bearing sclerotia pretreated with 0.1% of mercuric chloride for one min before inoculation.
- Optimal temperatures for the germination of sclerotia of *Rhizoctonia solani* are 25 and 30°C.
- Treatment of sclerotia with 0.1% of sodium hypochlorite, potassium hydroxide and ethanol for one min are not effective for the isolation of *Rhizoctonia solani*.

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APPENDICES

Analysis of variance tables,(isolation on different media).
Isolation on different culture media

C.V = 14.61%

Pre heat treatment of sclerotia

Source of variation	D.F	S.S	M.S	F .value	prob
Between treatments	3	182.288	60.763	208.664	0.000
Within treatments	12	3.494	0.291		
Total	15	185.782			

C .V =14.38%

Incubation temperatures of sclerotia

Source of variation	D.F	S.S	M.S	F- value	Prob
Between treatments	3	177.957	59.319	480.153	0.000
Within treatments	12	1.483	0.124		
Total	15				

C . V= 10.40%

Surface disinfection of tubers

Source of variation	D.F	S.S	M.S	F-Value	Prob
Concentrations A	2	45.761	22.880	601.2335	0.000
Times B	2	45.761	22.880	601.2335	0.000
AB	4	91.521	22.880	601.2335	0.000
Error	27	1.028	0.038		
Total	35	184.070			

C.V=24.47%

Effects of various chemicals on sclerotial germination

Source of variation	D. F	S.S	M.S	F-value	Prob
Within treatments	3	0.14	0.047	1.00	0.4363
Between treatments	3	129.29	43.231	914.13	0.000
Error	9	0.43	0.047		
Total	15	130.26			